
LINGVOCULTUROLOGICAL STUDY AND CLASSIFICATION OF THE TERM "HEAD" AS A BODY

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Abstract.

Today, the issue of tolerance has acquired particular relevance - tolerance for people belonging to different nationalities and cultures. Recently, this problem has acquired particular importance because more and more often we began to notice manifestations of hostility, unfriendliness, anger, and aggressiveness. Moods of mutual intolerance and cultural selfishness penetrate the family and the school. Such trends negatively affect the development of the personality of children, their spirituality and kindness. That is why parents need to carefully consider the education of children's tolerance and find effective mechanisms that contribute to its formation.

Key words.

children, tolerance, teaching, indifference

People all over the world are different: a different race, nationality, culture, religion, social environment, health status, way of thinking. Tolerance is the life position of a person, which I have, it is easy for him to communicate with a variety of people, which means it is easier to live. Tolerance today has become a condition for harmonious life in society. That is why it became necessary to educate the younger generation according to the rules of tolerance.[1]

Currently, hostility, anger, aggressiveness are becoming more widespread in the children's environment. There are many reasons for this. Mutual intolerance and cultural selfishness through the social environment of children and families are increasingly penetrating into children's educational institutions. One of the most important functions of the school is to teach people to live together. It is at school that the child should get acquainted with tolerant attitudes. Tolerance education is relevant and in demand today, when, according to Federico Mayor, Director General of UNESCO, "Life in diversity is one of the sources of serious problems for the societies in which our children grow up.[2] In a world where the

interpenetration of different cultures is on the rise, teaching the values and skills of “social life” has become a primary task of education. Thus, the problem of tolerance at school is very relevant in our modern world. Awareness of these ideas leads to the adoption of the Declaration of Principles of Tolerance on General Conference of UNESCO in 1995.[2] In the Russian Federation in August 2001 was approved by the Federal Target Program "Formation of installations of tolerant consciousness and prevention of extremism in Russian society". At the suggestion of UNESCO the first decade of the new century is declared "The Decade of Peace and Non-Violence for Children planet", 2003 was declared by UNESCO "Year of Tolerance", and on November 16 the World Day of Tolerance.

Tolerance is an active moral position, psychological readiness for tolerance for the sake of positive interaction with people of another nation, culture, religion and social environment. Tolerance is a virtue through which peace can be achieved. Tolerance requires giving every person opportunities for social development without discrimination. This quality of personality is a component of the humanistic orientation of a person and is determined by its value attitude towards people around. The problem of tolerance can be attributed to the educational problem. The subject of intolerance at school is the national, religious, social, ethnic and gender affiliation of the child, as well as his interests, habits, hobbies, features of appearance.

In the socio-cultural situation, the school should become the place where favorable conditions for interethnic communication are created, where all children are instilled with respect, both for their own culture and for the cultures of other peoples, because it is in the educational process that situations of cultural, interethnic, interpersonal, formal and informal communication.[3] Purposeful involvement of teachers and parents in the process of forming tolerance among schoolchildren makes it possible to activate their pedagogical position and contributes to the revision by adults of their own evaluative attitude and behavior. An adult should help the child form a positive self-esteem and the ability to reflect on their actions. It is important that the acquired knowledge is emotionally colored, fixed in the child, transferred to the motives of actions, and acquire a motivating force. Further, the child himself pays attention to his behavior, analyzes and evaluates it. Here, only an invisible presence, a coordinating, guiding function, will be required from an adult.

So, the formation of tolerance is a movement towards a free humane personality and it should proceed with the help of a humanistic personality-oriented approach.

The upbringing of a tolerant personality is a complex process, carried out by the entire social reality surrounding the child, by society, under the influence of relationships in the family, the prevailing views and attitudes of its members towards other people and society as a whole, under the influence of communication with peers and other people.

In various sources on pedagogy and psychology, the meaning of the term "tolerance" is explained as tolerance, the desire and ability to establish and maintain communication with people who differ in some respect from the prevailing type or do not adhere to generally accepted opinions.[4] Tolerance is a difficult and rare achievement for the simple reason that the foundation of a community is group consciousness. People unite in the same community with those who share their beliefs, or with those who speak the same language or have the same culture. At the same time, association into a community can be carried out on various grounds: national, ethnic, social, professional, leisure.

The school as a social institution has great opportunities for educating tolerance in children. These opportunities can be realized both in the process of educational and extracurricular activities. It is in the school community that a child can develop humanistic values and a real readiness for tolerant behavior.[5] The upbringing of a tolerant personality is a complex process, carried out by the entire social reality surrounding the child, by society, under the influence of relationships in the family, the prevailing views and attitudes of its members towards other people and society as a whole, under the influence of communication with peers and other people. As the analysis of practice shows, the above process occurs spontaneously. In order to make it purposeful, in our opinion, organized pedagogical activity at school is necessary. Today, when there is a violation of family ties, alienation of adults and children, increased conflict in their relationships, the vacuum into which many students fall can be filled by the full-fledged work of school teachers with pupils.

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